

RESPONSE PAPER**LAST NAME: NGNIE TETA****FIRST NAME: Ismael****PROGRAM CODE: DBIO****COURSE CODE: ACA-401D****PERIOD NUMBER: 1****INSTRUCTOR: DR. GULMA****Edit or delete text to show the actual information below:**

The author applied US UK conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics

The student must use Turabian (parenthetical/in-text references)

The author did use Zotero to insert references

The author did did not use Grammarly Premium

My plagiarism rate (per Grammarly Premium) is: 0%

The author used the following software: Microsoft Word on Microsoft Office 365 suite.

List of Key Concepts:

1. Researching the Topic (EUCLID 2021, 7)
2. Referencing the Essay (EUCLID 2021, 11)
3. American vs. British English (EUCLID 2021, 24-32)
4. Plagiarism (EUCLID 2021, 33-39)
5. Chicago Style and Usage (EUCLID 2021, 48)

GOOD ESSAY WRITING

1)INTRODUCTION

My choice to undertake a new academic adventure at the doctorate level took time due to my busy professional schedule. Passionate about studies and research, the ethical and bioethical topic an intrigue that I have been dragging with me for the past twenty years that I have been practicing in the academic field. The dynamics of research ethics committees, sometimes ambiguous in Africa and elsewhere, fascinate me. I knew I had to pursue this dream, and distance education was my only reasonable option. I discovered Euclid and conducted several searches on the institution's credibility before making my choice. I am sure it will be a fascinating journey.

This first ACA-401D course is crucial even for experienced researchers because it refers us to the fundamentals, attention to detail, and respect for the orthodoxy of academic writing. English is not my first language – I am rather French-speaking of Cameroonian origin, having pursued my post-secondary studies in French- Canada. This course is therefore essential because it will allow me at the same time to firm up my English fluency.

For this first work, I chose seven themes from the reading of the synopsis, namely 1) Introduction, 2) Researching the Topic, 3) Referencing the Essay, 4) American vs. British English, 5) Plagiarism, 6) Chicago Style and Usage 7) References.

2) RESEARCHING THE TOPIC

Researching the topic is the most compelling component of any essay work. Chapter one of the course provides simple and practical guidance on successful academic essay writing. Any successful dissertation begins with a good definition of its subject. A well-defined topic will save time and effort while ensuring the best search results. Once the subject is defined and the scope of research clarified, searching literature on the topic implies asking yourself critical questions about the type and usefulness of material you need to read.

I have noted that making notes as you read is critical, as we can only sometimes rely on our memory. It is also advisable to underline or highlight relevant information whether you read online or printed material. The course material EUCLID (2021, 8) also recommends having a reading list, ideally based on suggested readings by the professor, the supervisor, or any other credible source. While scanning through the document, it is advisable to flag the pages with relevant information so one can return for deeper understanding.

I have also noted that the student should use a critical thinking approach to widen his thoughts, which could be done through brainstorming or mind mapping. The course material EUCLID (2021, 9) also emphasizes the need to include evidence that agrees with our hypothesis and different views from authors who oppose our argument.

3) REFERENCING AND EDITING THE ESSAY

Chapter one of the course material (Euclid 2021, 11-12) shows the student how to reference and edit the essay (EUCLID 2021 11-12). It is highlighted upfront that “all academic essays MUST contain a reference. References guard against plagiarism which is a serious academic offense.” I have learned in this chapter that EUCLID accepts any form of referencing as long as there is consistency throughout the paper.

This section also stresses the vital role of editing in order to improve the essay quality. Editing the essay after a few days (rather than soon after the writing) helps to think further and have a fresher perspective of our work.

4) AMERICAN VS. BRITISH ENGLISH

Despite an infinity of similarities, British English and American English stand out from each other by a few differences. These differences are due to historical linguistic

influences from other countries; as in any culture, the practice has gradually changed the spelling and lexicon on each side of the Atlantic. Chapter 3 of the ACA-401 course book is dedicated to similitudes and differences between American and British English (EUCLID 2021, 25-32).

I have noted in this chapter that sometimes the two countries may have different pronunciations but the same spelling, different spelling but the same Pronunciation, and differences in grammar, syntax, punctuation, and general usage. Some concepts also have different terms or expressions. I have also learned that punctuation may differ in formal versus social letters; for the latter, an example given in the book is Dear Mr Smith, (GB) Dear Aunt Sally, (GB) versus Dear Mr. Smith: (US) (EUCLID 2021, 32).

As a Francophone, originally from Cameroon (a former British colony), haven studied in Canada, and now working in Kenya, I anticipate struggling to comply with the EUCLID rule of not mixing both English, but I will do my best.

5) PLAGIARISM

Chapter four on plagiarism is an important one that resonates even more with the bioethics courses. Plagiarism can be the act of appropriating someone else's creative work and presenting it as our own (EUCLID 2021, 33). It also refers to the fact of monopolizing extracts of texts, images, or data. All this, coming from external sources to integrate them into his own work without mentioning the provenance. This can also be translated as summarizing an author's original idea, expressing it in your own words while omitting to mention the source.

This lesson insists on how to avoid plagiarism. The easiest way to do so is to always cite the sources of information. This presupposes the student needs to prepare his essays before the last minute as a last-minute rush increases the temptation of plagiarism. I have also noted that the chapter provides specific examples of plagiarism and tips on giving credit to an author.

6) CHICAGO STYLE AND USAGE

I have learned in this chapter five that EUCLID recommends the Chicago Rules (Turabian). Chicago style, if chosen by the student for his work, should therefore be used on all the aspects of the document, including preferred sentence lengths, the fonts, the spelling (UK versus US, for example), the abbreviations, the terminology, the symbols, the structure, the voice preferences (EUCLID 2021, 41).

REFERENCES

EUCLID. “ACA-401D: International Academic Writing (Doctorate) – EUCLID University LMS.” Accessed July 23, 2023. <https://eucliduniversity.net/courses/aca-401d/>.

Cleenewerck, Laurent and Kabiru Gulma. 2021. *ACA-401/ACA-401D Coursepack: Period 1*. Fourth Ed. Bangui: Euclid University.

“Plagiarism | University of Oxford.” Accessed July 23, 2023. <https://www.ox.ac.uk/students/academic/guidance/skills/plagiarism>.

Cleenewerck, Laurent and Kabiru Abubakar Gulma. 2025. *ACA-401/ACA 401D Course Pack: Period 1*. 6th ed. Washington, D.C.: Euclid University Press. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15245536>.